

TIL - MILLAT KO'ZGUSI**Sobirov Ravshan Sobitjon o'g'li**

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ANNOTATSIYA: Mustaqillikka erishgandan so'ng tilga berilgan e'tibor va til taraqqiyoti qay darajada bo'lgani. Tilimizdan qay o'rinlarda foydalanilayotgani. Shu davr mobaynida tilimizning boyishi qanday kechdi?

Kalit so'zlar: til, millat, taraqqiyot

Til har bir millatning ko'zgusi, uning haqiqiy sarchashmasidir. Til bor ekan, millat barhayotdir. Tilni Onaga qiyoslanishi bejiz emas, inson o'z onasini ko'rmasdan, uning sof muhabbatini, mehrini tuymasdan yashay olishi mumkin emas. Bu fikrimizning isboti sifatida O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyev tomonidan o'zbek tiliga davlat tili maqomi berilganligining 30 yilligi munosabati bilan so'zlagan nutqini keltirishimiz mumkin: "Kimda-kim o'zbek tilining bor latofatini, jozibasi va ta'sir kuchini, cheksiz imkoniyatlarini his qilmoqchi bo'lsa, munis onalarimizning allalarini, ming yillik dostonlarimizni, o'lmas maqomlarimizni eshitsin, baxshi va hofizlarimizning sehrli qo'shiqlariga quloq tutsin". 1989-yil 21-oktyabr... Aynan shu kunda o'zbek tilining haqiqiy jozibasini anglashni boshlashga imkoniyat berildi. O'zbek millati uchun dunyoga tuynuk ochildi. 2020-yil 21-oktyabr... Roppa-rosa o'zbek tiliga davlat tili maqomi berilganligiga 31 yil to'ldi. Xo'sh, mana shu davr mobaynida o'zbek tilining haqiqiy jozibasi, uning go'zalligini dunyoga tanitish uchun qanday ishlar amalga oshirildi?

Ta'kidlab o'tish joizki, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasida o'zbek tili maqomi huquqiy jihatdan mustahkamlandi. O'zbek tili haqidagi qonun qabul qilinganidan so'ng barcha davlat hujjatlari o'zbek tilida yuritila boshlandi, gazeta va jurnallarning o'zbek tilida chop etilishi yo'lga qo'yildi. 1993-yil 2-sentyabrda "Lotin tiliga asoslangan o'zbek alifbosini tuzish to'g'risida"gi qonun qabul qilingandan so'ng, mamlakatimiz har tomonlama rivojlandi va jahon kommunikatsiya tizimidan munosib o'rin egallashiga yo'l ochdi. Shu o'rinda statistik ma'lumotlarga e'tibor qaratsak: dunyoda 5600 dan ortiq tillar mavjud bo'lib, bundan 200 tasigina davlat tili sifatida qabul qilingan. Ularning orasida o'zbek tilining borligi uning naqadar sof, mukammal, purma'no

va jozibadorligining yorqin dalilidir. Rossiyalik tilshunos olim, professor A.M.Kozlyanina “O‘zbek tili nafis va musiqa ohangidek jozibador” deb bejiz ta’kidlamagan edi.

Lekin, shu o‘rinda savol tug‘ilish tabiiy: nahotki o‘zbek tili biror bir joyga nom qo‘yish uchun ham yaroqli bo‘lmasa?! Afsus, barchamizga ma’lumki, ko‘chalarda do‘konlar, supermarketlar, turli xil ustaxona shoxobchalari, go‘zallik salonlari, turli xil osmono‘par binolar, bog‘chalarga qo‘yilgan nomlar o‘zbek tilida emas balki, boshqa xorij tillarida yozilganligining guvohi bo‘lishimiz mumkin. Bu haqiqatni isbotlash uchun siz ulkan bir ilmiy izlanish qilishingiz shart emas, aynan ko‘chaga otlanib turib, qo‘lingizga qalam va ruchka olgan holatda chiqsangiz kifoya. Naqadar achinarli holat bo‘lishiga qaramay, biz bunga ko‘nikib yashab kelmoqdamiz! Axir biz O‘zbekistonda yashayapmiz-ku, nima uchun unda joy nomlarini o‘zbek tilida nomlay olmaymiz? Buning uchun kim aybdor: davlat organlarimi yoki o‘zbek millatimi?

Ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda O‘zbekistonda osmono‘par binolar qurilayotgan bo‘lishiga qaramasdan, ularning nomi hali-hamon ingliz tilida ekanligi haqida bildirilgan turli xil fikrlarga duch kelishimiz mumkin. Misol uchun ularning birida yozilishicha, Toshkent shahrining markazida qurilgan “Nest one” deb nomlangan turar joy binosining nomi o‘zbek tilida emas, aynan ingliz tilida! Vaholanki, bu bino O‘zbekistonda, aynan o‘zbeklar tomonidan (inglizlar emas!) qurilgan-ku! Shuningdek, ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning birida yozilgan maqolada mana bu so‘zlarni ham uchratishimiz mumkin: “Xullas, bunyodkori o‘zbekmi, uning dastxati qurgan binosida yaqqol ko‘rinishi kerak va bu o‘sha quruvchining o‘zligini yo‘qotmaganidan darak beradi. Dastxat avvalo nomlarda namoyon bo‘ladi.

Ochig‘ini aytganda, rasmiy matbuotda o‘zbek tiliga bo‘lgan e‘tiborsizlik anchagina yuqori. Yana ham aniqrog‘i, bu borada davlat muassasalari yetakchilik qilib kelmoqda. Aslida ular tilshunoslarni jalb qilib bo‘lsa ham, o‘zbek tilining boyligini xalqqa namoyon etish, yangi so‘z va iboralarni o‘zbekcha talqinini joriy qilishda bosh qosh bo‘lishlari kerak”.

O‘zbek tilini rivojlantirish uchun quyidagi takliflarni keltirib o‘tamiz:

1. Ayni o‘zbek tili sohasi mutaxassislaridan O‘zbek tilini bilish darajasini tasdiqlovchi sertifikat olish tartibini ishlab chiqish; (Xuddi CEFR, IELTS yoki boshqa chet tili sertifikatlari shu til mutaxassislaridan so‘ralgani kabi);

2. Mjtkning 42-moddasiga: “Davlat organlari va tashkilotlarida ish yuritishda davlat tili haqidagi qonun hujjatlari talablariga rioya etmaslik, mansabdor shaxslarga bazaviy hisoblash miqdorining ikki baravaridan besh baravarigacha miqdorda jarima solishga sabab bo’ladi” degan o’zgartirish kiritish;

3. OAVda davlat tilining jozibadorligi xususidagi turli xil teledasturlar, davra suhbatlari, reklamalar, animatsion roliklar namoyish qilish; (faqatgina 21-oktyabr sanasida emas, doimiy ravishda olib borilishini ta’minlash joiz);

4. Chet el fuqarolari ishtirokida o’zbek tilini madh etadigan xalqaro insho, tezis, maqola, ocherklar tanlovlarini tashkil qilish va ularni rag’batlantirish (bu taklif ham faqatgina 21-oktyabr Til bayrami kuni uchun emas, doimiy ravishda olib borilishi maqsadga muvofiq).

Xulosa qiladigan bo’lsak, har birimiz davlat tiliga bo’lgan e’tiborni mustaqillikka bo’lgan e’tibor deb, davlat tiliga ehtirom va sadoqatni ona Vatanga ehtirom va sadoqat deb bilishimiz, shunday qarashni hayotimiz qoidasiga aylantirishimiz lozimligini butun vujudimiz bilan his etishimiz lozim. Bunday vatanparvar harakatni barchamiz o’zimizdan, o’z oilamiz va jamoamizdan boshlashimiz bilanoq o’zbek tilini rivojlantirishga bevosita ulkan hissa qo’shgan bo’lamiz. Zero, buyuk ma’rifatparvar bobomiz Abdulla Avloniy yozganidek: «Har bir millatning dunyoda borlig’ini ko’rsatadurg’on oyinai hayoti tili va adabiyotidir. Milliy tilni yo’qotmak millatning ruhini yo’qotmakdur».

Ушбу мақолада ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУҒАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолилик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris "Devonu lugotit turk" in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

⁵ Bakhriddinova, B. M. (2020). "DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK" AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

Мамлакатимиз тараққиётининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.⁹

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹⁰

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory. Opinions on the importance of translation among different peoples, the concept of translation, and its types are discussed. However, various examples of translation types are given.¹¹

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹²

This article analyzes how Somerset Maugham's short story "A Friend in Need" skillfully reflects the power and value of true friendship using ethical concepts such as goodness, kindness, justice, and compassion, which are sacred to each of us.¹³

⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

⁹ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

¹⁰ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.

¹¹ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

¹² Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

¹³ Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(2), 240-244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in “Tamburlaine the Great” by Christopher Marlowe.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

В современном обществе все более возрастает роль иностранных языков. Знание иностранного языка дает молодежи возможность приобщиться к мировой культуре, использовать в своей деятельности потенциал обширных ресурсов глобальной сети Интернет, а также работать с информационными и коммуникационными технологиями и мультимедийными средствами обучения.¹⁶

This article deals with the heroes of the novel “Between Two Doors”, one of the most popular works of modern Uzbek literature. There is a comprehensive analysis of the female image. A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel “Between Two Doors”. The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.¹⁷

Har bir millat madaniyatida kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi qarashlar mavjud bo'lib ular shu xalq dunyoqarashini, dinini, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzini va tarixini o'zida mujassamlashtiradi. Xususan, o'zbek va ingliz xalqi amaliy nutqida rak, sil, vabo kabi xavfli kasalliklar nomi qadimda tabulashtirilgan, bunga tarixiy sabablar mavjud. Hozirgi kunda ularning davosi topilgan bo'lsada, xalqimiz “yomon xastalik”, “og'ir dard”, “yomon kasallik” kabi birikmalarni qo'llash bilan kifoyalanadi.¹⁸

¹⁴ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY “TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT”. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

¹⁶ Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.

¹⁷ Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov's Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

¹⁸ Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6509637>

Badiiy adabiyotning qamrov darajasi keng sanaladi. Zero undagi janrlarning har biri insonning kamoloti uchun xizmat qiladi.¹⁹

В данной статье сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского.²⁰

В настоящее время глобальной социальной опасностью является угроза обнищания населения. Безработица, экономическая и социальная нестабильность, несбыточность надежд, крушение планов интенсифицируют процесс маргинализация населения.²¹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day. This article will highlight the important aspects of the study of culture and national characteristics in the study of modern units of oral speech. Currently, English is widely spoken in the world community. It is the language of Advanced Science and technology, trade and cultural relations, trade and business.²²

The article is dedicated to the description of Uzbek national children's clothes of the past centuries and its modern implementation. Article describes types of clothes, its designation and modern usage.²³

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

1. Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУФАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

¹⁹ Oripova Kamola. (2022). O'ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(3), 398–408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>

²⁰ Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Хамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.

²¹ Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.

²² NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

²³ Kadirova, N. A. (2020). UZBEK NATIONAL CHILDRENS CLOTHING AND ITS EVOLUTION. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 155-157.

2. Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies, 5(7), 40-45.
3. Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. Oriental Art and Culture, (III), 440-444.
4. Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 9(11), 22-28.
5. Bakhridinova, B. M. (2020). "DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK" AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. Theoretical & Applied Science, (4), 981-985.
6. Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions, 2(05), 211-215.
7. Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." JournalNX, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.
8. Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>
9. Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. European science review, (3-4), 69-72.
10. Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.
11. Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies, 24(2), 35-40.
12. Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. International Journal of Biomedicine, 6(1), 38-40.

13. Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(2), 240-244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>
14. Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.
15. Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.
16. Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. *Коммуникативный метод. Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.
17. Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov's Book "Between Two Doors"). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.
18. Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6509637>
19. Oripova Kamola. (2022). O'ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(3), 398-408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>
20. Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Хамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.
21. Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.
22. NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).
23. Kadirova, N. A. (2020). UZBEK NATIONAL CHILDRENS CLOTHING AND ITS EVOLUTION. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 155-157.